

Supplemental Table 11. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between abuse and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Study population	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Abuse categories	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
Alhusen, J. L.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 2004-11 and completed the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System survey	251 342	Odds of excessive GWG increased by experiencing intimate partner violence (IPV) before pregnancy	NS effect of IPV before and/or during pregnancy on insufficient GWG; NS effect of IPV during or before and during pregnancy on excessive GWG	No intimate partner violence (IPV); IPV before pregnancy only; IPV during pregnancy only; IPV before and during pregnancy	No	S & NS
Berenson, A. B.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents <18 years who received prenatal care at an adolescent obstetrics clinic (single-site)	337	Higher odds of insufficient GWG in adolescents who were physically abused (vs. no abuse)		Battered during pregnancy (yes/no)	Yes	S
Beydoun, H. A.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-06 Oklahoma Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System who were ≥20 years of age	11 561	Physical violence by an intimate partner around the time of pregnancy (before and/or during) was positively and significantly associated with insufficient and excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) only among women ≥35 years	Physical abuse before and/or during pregnancy not associated with excessive or insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) in younger women (age 20 - 34 years)	Physical intimate partner violence (IPV) before and/or pregnancy (yes/no)	No	S & NS
Gentry, J.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Participants from a smoking intervention program (a multi-site program) in Northeast Tennessee; women who experienced physical or sexual interpartner violence were excluded to assess the independent effect of psychosocial violence	489		NS difference in total GWG based on experiencing psychological abuse vs not experiencing psychological abuse	Any psychological abuse (yes/no)	No	NS
Gisladdottir, A.	2014	Iceland	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth between 1993 and 2011; a registry with women who sought services for sexual assault was used to identify women having experienced abuse	2 556		NS difference in adequacy of GWG (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) between women who experienced sexual abuse and those who did not	Experienced sexual abuse (yes/no; based on receiving services from the Rape Trauma Service)	No	NS

Johnson, P. J.	2002	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Primarily low-income, urban women seeking prenatal care at a specific clinic from 1997-98	578	<u>In adults:</u> higher odds for insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if any report of abuse (vs. no abuse; type and timing of abuse not considered), history of physical abuse only, history of physical abuse with or without history of physical abuse; higher odds of excessive GWG if history of sexual abuse with or without history of physical abuse, any abuse <u>When all subjects grouped together:</u> higher odds of insufficient GWG if history of physical abuse only	<u>In adolescents:</u> NS association between insufficient and excessive GWG and any type or timing of abuse; <u>in adults:</u> NS effect on odds of insufficient or excessive GWG if a woman experienced physical or sexual abuse during pregnancy; NS effect on odds of excessive GWG if a woman had a history of physical abuse only <u>When all ages grouped together:</u> NS effect of current physical/sexual abuse, history of sexual abuse with or without physical abuse, or any abuse on odds of insufficient or excessive GWG; NS effect of history of physical abuse only on odds of excessive GWG	No abuse; current physical and/or sexual abuse; history of physical abuse only; history of sexual abuse with or without history of physical abuse; any abuse	Yes	S & NS
Kearney, M. H.	2004	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1985	Multi-site study with women in Massachusetts who were screened during pregnancy for intimate partner abuse (non-representative sample)	1 969	Abuse is a weak predictor of insufficient GWG (<15 lbs)		Any physical or emotional abuse within past year (yes/no)	No	S
McFarlane, J.	1996	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 1985	Primarily low-income women attending one of two public prenatal clinics in Texas and Maryland; ethnic composition: about 1/3 White, 1/3 Black, 1/3 Hispanic	1 058	Higher relative risk of insufficient GWG (<15lbs) if abused during pregnancy (vs not abused)		Abused during pregnancy (yes/no)	Yes	S
Ranchod, Y. K.	2016	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, and Hispanic women who participated in the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth	6 199	Exposure to physical abuse during childhood was associated with higher risk of excessive GWG		Physical abuse during childhood (yes/no)	No	S

Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for total GWG: negative association with experiencing physical abuse by baby's father Multivariate logistic regression for insufficient GWG (<21 lbs for underweight/normal weight women, <10 lbs for overweight/obese women): For overweight/obese women: increased risk of insufficient GWG if physical abuse by baby's father	In underweight/normal weight women: NS effect of abuse by baby's father	Physical abuse by baby's father (yes/no)	Yes	S & NS
Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were ≥18 years old	1 988		NS effect of experiencing physical abuse before or during pregnancy on general adequacy of GWG (looked at distribution of women in insufficient, adequate and excessive categories)	Physical abuse during or before pregnancy (yes/no)	Yes	NS
Yang, M. S.	2006	Taiwan	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; no GWG guideline identified	Indigenous women in Southern and Eastern Taiwan who gave birth from January-December 2003 at one of 10 hospitals	1 143	Lower GWG in women with physical abuse by intimate partner during pregnancy (as compared to no physical abuse)		Physical abuse during pregnancy (yes/no)	Yes	S